

Predicting LLM Training and Inference Runtime: A Survey of Methods, Datasets, and Open Challenges

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Abstract

Large language models have become the dominant workload in modern GPU clusters, driving unprecedented demand for compute during both training and inference. Yet GPU clusters typically operate at only 30–50% utilization, largely because schedulers rely on user-provided runtime estimates that are notoriously inaccurate. Running thousands of LLM inference requests through shared datacenters further compounds this underutilization. Accurate runtime prediction is a key enabler of LLM efficiency: it supports shortest-job-first scheduling, backfilling, dynamic resource allocation, and cost-aware instance selection, while providing NLP practitioners with reliable completion estimates for training runs and serving latency guarantees. However, LLM workloads pose unique prediction challenges: attention complexity scales quadratically with sequence length, autoregressive decoding produces variable-length outputs, and 3D parallelism creates intricate performance interactions. This survey systematically reviews runtime prediction methods with emphasis on LLM training and inference workloads, presenting a feature taxonomy, analyzing design choices of existing prediction methods, surveying public datasets and highlighting their limitations. We identify applications critical to LLM efficiency and key open challenges including generalization to rapidly evolving model architectures and hardware.

1 Introduction

The unprecedented scale of large language models has made GPU compute the primary bottleneck for NLP research and deployment. Global data center investment reached \$500 billion in 2024—nearly doubled since 2022—driven overwhelmingly by AI and GPU buildout (International Energy Agency, 2025), with LLM training and inference accounting for a rapidly growing share of this demand (Cotter et al., 2025). Yet GPU clusters operate inefficiently: production systems report only 30–50%

utilization (Jeon et al., 2019; Hu et al., 2021). A fundamental contributor to this waste is that cluster schedulers depend on user-submitted runtime estimates to make allocation and scheduling decisions, and these estimates are notoriously inaccurate.

The consequences of inaccurate estimates are severe from both the cluster and user perspectives. When users *underestimate* runtime, jobs are killed before completion. When users *overestimate*, schedulers reserve resources for longer than necessary, preventing shorter jobs from being backfilled into the resulting gaps and leaving GPUs idle, reducing overall cluster throughput. This estimation burden particularly affects NLP practitioners, who routinely face complex scheduling decisions: training or fine-tuning LLMs for downstream tasks, running multi-benchmark evaluations, conducting hyperparameter sweeps for SFT or RLHF, and serving LLMs under latency SLOs. Without reliable runtime information, users must engage in costly trial-and-error to set time limits, cannot plan experiments within compute budgets, and lack trustworthy completion estimates for long-running jobs (Faisal et al., 2024).

Accurate runtime prediction can directly address these problems by replacing unreliable user estimates with data-driven forecasts. On the cluster side, predictions enable shortest-job-first (SJF) scheduling, which minimizes average completion time but requires duration knowledge rarely available in practice—without it, operators resort to FIFO scheduling, leading to head-of-line blocking (Gu et al., 2019). Beyond scheduling order, runtime predictions enable backfilling idle resources with short jobs, dynamic resource allocation, and cost-aware selection between spot and on-demand instances (Peng et al., 2018; Qiao et al., 2021). On the user side, predictions provide reliable completion estimates and eliminate the need for manual time budgeting, allowing practitioners to focus on model development rather than cluster logistics.

However, predicting LLM runtime poses unique challenges that make this problem especially difficult for NLP workloads. First, LLMs exhibit complex dependencies on interacting factors: model architecture, hardware platform, and distributed training strategy. Second, the NLP landscape evolves rapidly—methods validated on earlier architectures may fail on modern transformers, and predictions for V100 GPUs may not transfer to H100 accelerators. LLM-specific complexity is substantial: attention scales quadratically with sequence length, autoregressive decoding produces variable-length outputs, and 3D parallelism with memory optimization techniques like ZeRO (Rajbhandari et al., 2020) creates intricate performance interactions. NLP workloads also exhibit distinctive patterns—varying sequence lengths across datasets, different decoding strategies, and iterative prompt engineering workflows that generate many short jobs. Third, a fundamental tension exists between prediction accuracy and inference latency: sophisticated models achieve higher accuracy but may be too slow for real-time scheduling decisions (Liu et al., 2025).

Motivated by the efficiency needs of NLP and LLM practitioners, this survey provides a comprehensive review of runtime prediction for deep learning jobs, with particular emphasis on LLM training and inference workloads. We examine features and input representations (§3), design choices of existing prediction methods (§4), public datasets and limitations (§5), and applications with open challenges (§6).

2 Background and Problem Definition

This section establishes the technical foundation for runtime prediction in deep learning systems. We describe the computational structure of training and inference pipelines, then formalize the prediction problem.

2.1 Deep Learning Training and Inference

Training proceeds through iterative optimization of model parameters. Each iteration consists of a forward pass computing the loss, a backward pass computing gradients (roughly twice the computation of the forward pass), an optional communication phase synchronizing gradients across workers in distributed settings, and a parameter update step. Total training time depends on per-iteration time and the number of iterations required for convergence. For LLMs, training encompasses distinct

Category	Example Features
<i>Job-Level</i>	
Architecture	Model Type, Layers, Parameters, Operator Types
Configuration	Batch Size, Optimizer, Mixed Precision
Scope	Epochs, Dataset Size, Checkpoint Frequency
Code & Framework	Frameworks Used, Source Code Semantics
<i>Hardware</i>	
Compute	GPU Model, CUDA/Tensor Cores, Peak FLOPS
Memory	HBM Capacity, Bandwidth, Cache Hierarchy
Interconnect	NVLink/PCIe, InfiniBand/Ethernet, Topology
Allocation	GPU Count, Node Count, CPU Cores
<i>Cluster State</i>	
Availability	Utilization, Fragmentation
Interference	Co-location Contention, Network Congestion
Historical	User History, Job Similarity, Model/Dataset Cache

Table 1: Feature Taxonomy for Runtime Prediction

phases with different runtime characteristics: *pre-training* on large corpora dominates total compute and runs for weeks to months; *supervised fine-tuning* (SFT) adapts the model to specific tasks with shorter but highly variable durations depending on dataset size; and *reinforcement learning from human feedback* (RLHF) introduces additional complexity through reward model inference interleaved with policy optimization, making per-iteration time less predictable.

Inference executes only the forward pass, but introduces distinct prediction challenges. For LLM inference specifically, execution consists of two phases with very different performance profiles: the *prefill* phase processes the entire input prompt in parallel, while the *decode* phase generates tokens autoregressively one at a time. Modern LLM serving systems add further complexity through continuous batching, KV-cache management, and speculative decoding, all creating interactions that affect both latency and throughput prediction.

2.2 Problem Formulation

Let \mathcal{J} denote job specifications (model architecture, training/inference configuration), \mathcal{H} denote hardware configurations (GPU types, quantities, topology), and \mathcal{S} denote cluster states (resource availability, concurrent workloads). A predictor $\hat{f} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{S} \rightarrow T$ maps these inputs to predicted runtime T . Throughout this survey, **runtime** refers to execution time—the wall-clock duration from when a job begins running on allocated resources until completion, excluding queue wait time. Given historical executions $\mathcal{D} = \{(J_i, H_i, S_i, T_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, the objective is:

$$\min_{\hat{f}} E_{(J,H,S,T) \sim P_{test}} \left[\mathcal{L}(\hat{f}(J, H, S), T) \right] \quad (1)$$

3 Features and Input Representations

The effectiveness of duration prediction depends critically on the features used to characterize jobs, hardware, and cluster state. This section presents a systematic taxonomy of features and input representations employed across the literature.

3.1 Job-Level Features

Job-level features describe the workload independent of execution environment. **Model architecture** features such as layer count, parameter count, and operator types directly determine computational complexity and memory footprint, making them essential for accurate runtime prediction (Gao et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2025). **Training configuration** features including batch size, learning rate, optimizer choice, mixed precision settings, and gradient accumulation steps significantly affect per-iteration time and convergence behavior (Peng et al., 2018). **Scope features** such as total epochs, dataset size, and checkpoint frequency determine the total amount of work, though early stopping introduces prediction uncertainty. **Framework and code features** capture implementation details: framework choice, library versions, and distributed training strategy affect kernel selection and execution patterns (Weng et al., 2022). Algorithm complexity and data access patterns can also be extracted from source code to improve prediction accuracy (Wang et al., 2025b). For LLM workloads specifically, additional features become critical: *sequence length* and *context window size* directly affect attention computation and memory usage; *vocabulary size* and *number of attention heads* determine embedding and attention overhead; *quantization level* (INT4/INT8/FP16) drastically changes both compute and memory requirements; and *serving batch strategies* such as continuous batching and PagedAttention (Kwon et al., 2023) impact runtime in inference settings.

3.2 Hardware Features

Hardware features characterize the computational resources allocated to a job. **GPU compute capabilities** include the number of CUDA and tensor cores, peak FLOPS, and clock frequencies, which directly determine computational throughput and serve as key inputs for establishing roofline performance bounds in runtime prediction (Lee et al., 2025). **Memory system features** encompass HBM capacity, memory bandwidth, and cache hi-

erarchy, which determine whether workloads are compute-bound or memory-bound and thus significantly affect predicted execution time (Williams et al., 2009). **Interconnect and network topology**, including NVLink versus PCIe for intra-node communication and InfiniBand versus Ethernet for inter-node transfers, critically affect distributed training performance by determining communication overhead (Amaral et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2023). **Allocation features** including GPU count, number of nodes, and CPU cores determine the degree of parallelism.

3.3 Cluster State Features

Cluster state features capture the dynamic execution context that affects job runtime. **Interference features** capture performance degradation from co-located workloads during execution, including network congestion and memory bandwidth contention, which cause IPC degradation and cache miss rate increases that significantly impact runtime (Hu et al., 2021). **Resource fragmentation** patterns affect runtime when jobs cannot obtain contiguous resources, leading to suboptimal communication topologies (Weng et al., 2023). **Historical features** leverage past execution data: user submission history and job similarity metrics provide strong baselines for predicting runtime of recurring workloads.

Takeaway

Job-level, hardware, and cluster state features interact in complex ways. LLM workloads add critical features—sequence length, quantization level, serving batch strategy—that are absent from traditional HPC feature sets. Robust prediction requires the full spectrum.

4 Methods

We organize this section around four core technical challenges that any runtime prediction system must address: *what information to use* (§4.1), *at what granularity to predict* (§4.2), *how to generalize beyond training data* (§4.3), and *how to cope with limited data* (§4.4). This organization reveals how different methods—from simple historical averages to physics-informed neural networks—represent distinct design choices along these axes, and why hybrid approaches that combine analytical mod-

Figure 1: Design axes for runtime prediction methods with representative works. Each axis represents a core technical challenge; methods are positioned by their design choices along these axes.

els with physical constraints currently achieve the strongest results.

4.1 Input Representation

The choice of input representation sets the ceiling on prediction accuracy: no model can recover information absent from its inputs. We identify five levels of input richness, each enabling progressively more powerful prediction.

Job metadata is the most widely available input, consisting of user ID, queue name, requested resources, and wallclock estimates. The majority of HPC prediction work operates at this level using standard ML models: linear regression (Tsafrir et al., 2007; Rauschmayr, 2015; Gaussier et al., 2015; Tanash et al., 2019), random forests (McKenna et al., 2016; Tanash et al., 2019, 2021a,b; Yang et al., 2023), decision trees (McKenna et al., 2016; Chen and Guestrin, 2016; Guo et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020; Tanash et al., 2019; Zrigui et al., 2022), SVR (Park and Kim, 2017; Fan et al., 2017), kNN and instance-based methods (Sonmez et al., 2009; Matsunaga

and Fortes, 2010; McKenna et al., 2016; Cunha et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021; Galleguillos et al., 2017), MLPs (Hou et al., 2019; Yildirim et al., 2026). Remarkably, even the simplest approach—averaging a user’s last two runtimes (Tsafrir et al., 2007)—consistently outperforms user estimates, underscoring how poor user predictions are. However, metadata-only methods treat jobs as black boxes and cannot distinguish workloads with identical resource requests but vastly different computational profiles.

Job scripts and source code break open the black box. McKenna et al. (2016) showed that using job scripts as sole input outperforms metadata-based approaches by 51%. Prionn (Wyatt et al., 2018) goes further by encoding entire job scripts as character matrices via word2vec embeddings, feeding them to neural network processing and achieving 98% median accuracy across 300K jobs. AREL (Cheon et al., 2021) translates MPI source code into finite automata, extracting structural program features for runtime prediction.

Semantic code understanding via LLMs rep-

resents the latest advance, and is particularly relevant for NLP workloads where training scripts commonly specify model architectures by HuggingFace model name, load datasets from the HuggingFace Hub, and configure distributed training through frameworks like DeepSpeed, FSDP, or Megatron-LM. SchedMate (Wang et al., 2025b) deploys a ReAct-style LLM agent that autonomously explores job repositories, extracting model architecture, dataset, and training configuration as structured metadata. ORA (Liu et al., 2025) encodes both metadata and script content into dense vectors for similarity-based retrieval. These approaches can understand *what* a job computes, not merely *how* it is configured.

Computation graphs provide exact structural information for DNN workloads. DNNPerf (Gao et al., 2023) represents models as DAGs where nodes carry operator-level features (type, hyperparameters, tensor shapes, FLOPs) and edges encode data dependencies, using an attention-based node-edge encoder for message passing. Decima (Mao et al., 2019) applies GNNs to job dependency DAGs for scheduling decisions. ScaleDL (Wang et al., 2025a) uses GNNs to capture cross-layer interactions such as kernel fusion and memory reuse.

Hardware specifications—peak FLOPS, memory bandwidth, cache hierarchy, and blocking parameters—enable physics-grounded prediction. The Roofline model (Williams et al., 2009) uses only peak compute and bandwidth to bound performance. Paleo (Qi et al., 2017) combines per-layer FLOPs with hardware specs. Habitat (Yu et al., 2021) leverages the invariance of operational intensity across GPUs for cross-hardware scaling. NeuSight (Lee et al., 2025) uses GPU tile dimensions and memory hierarchy parameters as inputs to specialized predictors. This category uniquely enables prediction on hardware that has never been profiled.

4.2 Prediction Granularity

A second key design choice is *at what level* to predict: treating a job as an indivisible unit, or decomposing it into smaller, more predictable components.

End-to-end prediction maps job descriptions directly to total runtime. This includes all approaches from Section §4.1, except the fine-grained approaches discussed in the next paragraph. End-to-end methods are simple to deploy but treat the relationship between job characteristics and runtime

as a monolithic function, limiting generalization to unseen configurations.

Fine-grained prediction decomposes computation at progressively finer granularities—layer, operator, and tile—each exposing more structure for accurate prediction. At the layer level, Paleo (Qi et al., 2017) analytically estimates FLOPs and data movement per layer, supporting both data and model parallelism; ScaleDL (Wang et al., 2025a) extends this with nonlinear per-layer models and GNNs to capture inter-layer dependencies such as kernel fusion and memory reuse. At the operator level, DNNPerf (Gao et al., 2023) predicts within computation graphs at operator granularity by capturing operator parallelism and data flow dependencies that layer-level analysis misses. At the finest granularity, NeuSight (Lee et al., 2025) decomposes each kernel into GPU-native tiles and predicts tile execution using specialized MLPs per operation type, yielding 8.9% error versus 140% for monolithic MLP prediction. The key insight unifying all three levels is that *finer decomposition dramatically improves generalization*: sub-unit behavior is governed by a small number of hardware parameters and composes predictably into whole-job runtime.

4.3 Generalization Strategies

Another primary design consideration is out-of-distribution (OOD) generalization, which is predicting on unseen hardware, model architectures, or shifting workloads. Different strategies address different types of distribution shift.

Online learning and incremental adaptation address temporal drift as workloads evolve. Zrigui et al. (Zrigui et al., 2022) train classifiers on rolling windows of recent weeks, continuously adapting to workload changes. OKCM (Li et al., 2021) combines online KNN with a correction mechanism that adjusts predictions in real time. ORA (Liu et al., 2025) incrementally updates its retrieval database without retraining, using diff-based contextual learning to highlight what changed between similar jobs.

Physics-informed constraints enable generalization to unseen hardware by encoding physical invariants. The Roofline model (Williams et al., 2009) provides hard bounds: performance cannot exceed peak FLOPS or peak bandwidth \times operational intensity. Extensions incorporate kernel launch overhead (Wang et al., 2020), multi-precision Tensor Core operations (Yang et al.,

2021), and cross-platform analysis (Wu et al., 2024). NeuSight (Lee et al., 2025) uses Roofline bounds to constrain ML predictions within physically plausible ranges—the model predicts device *utilization* rather than raw latency, with physics converting utilization to time. This physics-informed design is the primary reason NeuSight achieves strong OOD generalization.

Transfer learning addresses the cold-start problem when a target GPU lacks profiling data. Habitat (Yu et al., 2021) exploits the fact that a kernel’s arithmetic intensity is invariant across GPUs: it profiles on an available GPU, determines whether each kernel is compute- or memory-bound via the Roofline model, then scales execution time using ratios of compute units or memory bandwidths between source and target GPUs. For kernels where this wave scaling is insufficient, pre-trained MLPs learn the scaling relationship.

Structural decomposition enables generalization to unseen model architectures. By predicting at sub-model granularity (§4.2), systems can handle novel architectures as compositions of known components. ScaleDL (Wang et al., 2025a) combines layer-wise prediction with GNN-based interaction modeling, while NeuSight (Lee et al., 2025) achieves architecture-agnostic prediction through tile-level decomposition. Dai et al. (Dai et al., 2022) leverage runtime estimation within a distributed resource management framework for exascale systems, demonstrating that even approximate predictions improve scheduling at scale.

4.4 Data Efficiency

Collecting training data for runtime prediction is expensive: each data point requires actually running a job. Methods vary dramatically in how much data they require, from zero to millions of historical executions.

Analytical models require zero training data, deriving predictions entirely from hardware specifications and workload characteristics. Roofline (Williams et al., 2009) needs only peak FLOPS and memory bandwidth. Paleo (Qi et al., 2017) needs per-layer FLOPs and a platform efficiency parameter estimated from a handful of representative kernels. The cost is limited accuracy—these models assume ideal conditions that rarely hold in practice.

Minimal profiling strategies reduce data collection through principled sampling. ScaleDL (Wang et al., 2025a) employs D-optimal experimental de-

sign to select the most informative configurations for profiling, maximizing prediction accuracy per data point collected. Habitat (Yu et al., 2021) requires profiling on only *one* reference GPU and transfers predictions to other hardware via learned scaling factors.

Retrieval-augmented methods avoid retraining entirely by leveraging existing historical data at inference time. ORA (Liu et al., 2025) builds a continuously updated database of job embeddings, retrieving similar past jobs to inform predictions for new submissions. SchedMate (Wang et al., 2025b) computes semantic similarity between jobs using LLM-generated embeddings, predicting runtime from matched historical profiles.

History-based prediction can be surprisingly effective with minimal data. Tsafir et al. (Tsafir et al., 2007) demonstrated that averaging just the last two runtimes from the same user outperforms complex alternatives, suggesting that for recurring workloads, elaborate models may be unnecessary. At the other extreme, production-scale approaches like AMPRO-HPCC (Tanash et al., 2021a) leverage millions of historical Slurm records to train ensemble models, achieving strong performance through sheer data volume.

Takeaway

The four axes are interdependent: richer inputs enable finer granularity, which enables stronger generalization. Physics-informed constraints are the most effective generalization mechanism. For NLP practitioners: metadata-based methods suffice for recurring workloads; for cross-hardware or cross-architecture LLM prediction, combine structural decomposition with physical constraints.

5 Datasets

The availability of public cluster traces has been essential for advancing research on job runtime prediction. This section catalogs GPU cluster traces most relevant to deep learning runtime prediction. Table 2 summarizes these traces with their key features. A comprehensive catalog including CPU-only traces is provided in Appendix C, and evaluation metrics are discussed in Appendix B.

The traces span from early pre-transformer clusters (Philly (Jeon et al., 2019), Helios (Hu et al., 2021)) to recent LLM-era datasets. Alibaba’s GPU

Organization	Dataset	Scale	Period	Time-stamps	Resource Req.	Utilization	Source Code	Key Features
Microsoft	Philly (Jeon et al., 2019)	117K jobs	Aug–Dec 2017	✓	✓	✓		Per-minute GPU/CPU/memory utilization
SenseTime	Helios (Hu et al., 2021)	3.4M jobs	Apr–Sep 2020	✓	✓	✓		Largest public trace; 1.6M GPU jobs
Alibaba	GPU-v2020 (Weng et al., 2022)	6,500+ GPUs	2020	✓	✓	✓		61% training / 39% inference split
	GPU-v2023 (Weng et al., 2023)	6,200+ GPUs	2023	✓	✓	✓		Resource fragmentation analysis
	GPU-v2025 (Yang et al., 2025)	20K+ instances	2025	✓	✓	✓		DLRM inference workloads
	GenAI-v2026 (Yanying Lin, 2025) (Yanying Lin and Ye, 2026)	Large-scale	2026	✓	✓	✓		Diffusion & LLM model serving
Azure	LLM '23 (Patel et al., 2025)	1-day trace	2023	✓	✓			Input/output token counts
	LLM '24 (Stojkovic et al., 2025)	1-week trace	2024	✓	✓			Extended LLM inference trace
	LMM '25 (Qiu et al., 2026)	1-week trace	2025	✓	✓			Large multimodal model inference
Shanghai AI Lab	Acme (Hu et al., 2024)	881K jobs	Mar–Aug 2023	✓	✓	✓		LLM training
SchedMate	Mars (Wang et al., 2025b)	500 jobs	—	✓	✓	✓	✓	Source code for 7B–100B LLM jobs

Table 2: GPU cluster traces for deep learning runtime prediction. All listed traces contain GPU workloads relevant to training or inference prediction. **Resource Req.** = resource requests (e.g., GPU count). Mars is the only trace with source code (non-public). See Table 3 in the Appendix for a comprehensive list including CPU-only traces.

series (Weng et al., 2022, 2023; Yang et al., 2025; Yanying Lin, 2025; Yanying Lin and Ye, 2026) captures the evolution of production workloads over six years, while Azure’s LLM inference traces (Patel et al., 2025; Stojkovic et al., 2025; Qiu et al., 2026) uniquely provide input/output token counts for sequence-length-dependent prediction research. Acme (Hu et al., 2024) is the first large-scale LLM training trace, and Mars (Wang et al., 2025b) is the only trace with job source code, though it is not publicly available. A key limitation across all traces is the near-universal absence of source code and detailed model specifications, which constrains research into code-aware prediction methods. Detailed descriptions of each trace are provided in Appendix C.

6 Applications and Open Challenges

This section examines practical applications of runtime prediction, then discusses open challenges and future research directions.

6.1 Applications

Runtime prediction serves as a foundational capability for multiple cluster management tasks. While user-perceived completion time includes both queue wait and execution, predicting runtime alone enables schedulers to make informed ordering and placement decisions that minimize overall queue delays.

Job Scheduling. The primary application is enabling Shortest Job First (SJF) scheduling, which minimizes average job completion time by prioritizing jobs with shorter predicted runtimes. Since durations are unknown at submission, prediction-based approximations are necessary. Schedulers like Lucid (Hu et al., 2023) use predicted durations

directly for SJF-style ordering. 3Sigma (Park et al., 2018) argues that point estimates are insufficient given prediction uncertainty, instead scheduling based on full runtime distributions. PCS (Faisal et al., 2024) reframes the problem by co-designing prediction and scheduling to achieve both predictability and performance.

Backfilling. Backfilling uses predictions to fill scheduling gaps without delaying queued jobs. The scheduler identifies smaller jobs whose predicted duration fits within available time windows. Prediction accuracy directly impacts effectiveness: underestimation causes jobs to exceed their slots, while overestimation leaves resources idle. Machine learning-based prediction (Gaussier et al., 2015) improves backfilling efficiency over user-provided estimates, which are notoriously inaccurate.

Dynamic Resource Allocation. Prediction enables intelligent resource scaling during execution. Optimus (Peng et al., 2018) reallocates GPUs based on predicted remaining time, while Pollux (Qiao et al., 2021) predicts how throughput scales with resources, dynamically adjusting batch size and GPU count to maximize throughput.

Cost Optimization and User Experience. In cloud environments, prediction informs the cost-risk tradeoff between cheap but interruptible spot instances and reliable on-demand instances. Beyond system optimization, prediction improves user experience by providing completion time estimates, enabling better planning even when they don’t change actual completion times (Faisal et al., 2024).

LLM-Specific Applications. Runtime prediction benefits LLM workloads in several ways: training budget estimation lets researchers assess compute costs before committing to pre-training or fine-tuning; and predicted runtime informs experiment

planning for hyperparameter sweeps and model selection across architectures (e.g., dense vs. mixture-of-experts) under a fixed compute budget.

6.2 Open Challenges

Despite significant progress, substantial challenges remain for runtime prediction in production environments.

Generalization to Evolving LLM Architectures and Hardware. The most critical challenge is generalization beyond training distributions. New architectures—mixture-of-experts (MoE), state-space models, and multi-modal LLMs—each introduce fundamentally different computational patterns. LLM training also exhibits unpredictable dynamics such as Dynamic Sampling for post-training (Wei and Huang, 2026). On the hardware side, clusters increasingly span multiple GPU generations and new accelerators (TPUs, custom ASICs), yet naïve approaches exhibit dramatically higher error on unseen hardware; hybrid approaches combining learned patterns with analytical constraints generalize better (Lee et al., 2025).

Distributed Implementation Complexity. Modern 3D parallelism (data, tensor, pipeline) creates a vast configuration space with intricate interactions among communication patterns and hardware topology. Communication costs scale non-linearly due to collective operations and cluster-level contention (Cheon et al., 2021), while memory optimization techniques (ZeRO sharding, activation checkpointing, offloading) further alter computation–communication tradeoffs. Existing approaches model these effects through analytical (Qi et al., 2017) or GNN-based (Wang et al., 2025a) methods, but the combinatorial space of implementation choices remains a major challenge.

Accuracy Latency Trade-offs. A fundamental tension exists between prediction accuracy and inference latency. Simple models operate in microseconds, neural networks in milliseconds, and LLM-based predictors in seconds (Liu et al., 2025). For schedulers making decisions at job arrival during peak load, even millisecond latency may be prohibitive. The optimal model choice depends on scheduling context: backfilling decisions made periodically can tolerate higher latency, while pre-emption decisions favor simpler models.

LLM-Specific Prediction Difficulties. LLM workloads introduce unique challenges: variable-length generation makes inference runtime depend

on unknown output length; dynamic batching (continuous batching) causes per-request latency to depend on co-scheduled requests; and speculative decoding introduces stochastic acceptance rates. On the training side, sequence packing, curriculum learning, and dynamic data mixing change effective computation per iteration, making total runtime difficult to forecast from early iterations.

Data Availability. LLM-specific traces remain scarce and older traces predate transformer dominance. Critically, nearly all public traces lack job source code, preventing research into code-aware prediction (Wang et al., 2025b). Most traces also lack detailed model specifications or communication patterns, and organizations have incentives to keep operational data private.

Takeaway

Runtime prediction enables scheduling, backfilling, resource allocation, and LLM-specific optimizations such as training budget estimation. Key open challenges: generalization to evolving LLM architectures and hardware, LLM-specific difficulties (variable-length decoding, dynamic batching), and the near-universal absence of source code in public traces.

7 Conclusion

Runtime prediction is a key enabler of LLM efficiency, directly impacting the ability of the NLP community to train, fine-tune, and serve large language models within practical compute budgets. We surveyed the landscape from features and methods to datasets and applications, identifying three core limitations: (1) existing methods struggle to generalize to rapidly evolving LLM architectures and new hardware generations; (2) public traces almost universally lack job source code, blocking code-aware prediction research; and (3) LLM-specific challenges remain largely unaddressed. As LLMs become the foundation of NLP, efficient resource utilization directly impacts research accessibility and environmental sustainability. Future work should prioritize LLM-specific prediction methods, cross-architecture generalization, richer trace collection with source code, and rigorous evaluation to guide practical deployment in LLM serving and training infrastructure.

Limitations

While we emphasize OOD generalization as the central challenge, empirical evidence remains thin—most work evaluates on single clusters, and the reported 2.3% vs. 121% error gap (Lee et al., 2025) comes from one study. Our LLM-specific analysis relies on general principles rather than extensive validation, as public LLM traces remain scarce. Most papers report either accuracy or latency but rarely both, limiting our ability to characterize accuracy-latency trade-offs quantitatively. Many surveyed methods lack open-source implementations, so our comparative analysis relies on author-reported metrics. Finally, we focus on GPU clusters, excluding TPUs, custom ASICs, and non-deep-learning workloads.

Ethics and Broader Impacts

Prediction-driven scheduling can systematically disadvantage certain users or workload types through consistent underestimation or overestimation of runtime. Novel or unconventional jobs may be deprioritized or preempted more frequently, creating feedback loops that reinforce prediction bias against underrepresented workloads. Cluster operators should audit prediction systems for systematic biases across user groups and workload types. Some prediction approaches require detailed telemetry including source code (Wang et al., 2025b) or fine-grained metrics, raising privacy concerns in multi-tenant environments. Adversaries could also exploit prediction models to game scheduling systems or infer information about competitors’ workloads, so designers should consider adversarial robustness alongside accuracy. From an environmental perspective, better runtime prediction enables improved GPU utilization, which directly reduces the energy consumption and carbon footprint of LLM training and inference—a growing concern in the NLP community as models scale to hundreds of billions of parameters. By reducing the gap between allocated and actually used compute, prediction-driven scheduling can meaningfully contribute to more sustainable AI development.

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A Selection Process

This section describes our methodology for selecting papers and datasets included in this survey.

A.1 Paper Selection

We searched relevant top venues in systems, machine learning, and high-performance computing, focusing on papers addressing runtime or duration prediction for deep learning and GPU workloads. We primarily surveyed papers from 2007–2026, with a focus on recent advances in LLM-era prediction challenges while including selected earlier foundational works. The complete set of surveyed methods is organized in Figure 1.

The venues considered include:

- **Systems:** OSDI, SOSP, NSDI, ATC, EuroSys, ASPLOS, SoCC
- **High-Performance Computing:** SC, HPDC, ICS, ICPP, CLUSTER

- **Architecture:** ISCA, HPCA

We also included relevant works from journals (IEEE TPDS, JPDC, FGCS, Supercomputing) and arXiv preprints when they presented significant methodological contributions or unique datasets. We note that NLP venues (ACL, EMNLP, NAACL, COLM) have not yet published dedicated work on runtime prediction for LLM workloads, which we view as an opportunity for the NLP community to contribute domain-specific insights to this problem.

A.2 Dataset Selection

The datasets included in this survey (Table 2 and Table 3) were selected based on three criteria: (1) public availability or use in multiple published studies; (2) containing GPU workloads relevant to deep learning training or inference; and (3) providing sufficient metadata (timestamps, resource requests, utilization) for runtime prediction research. We searched GitHub repositories, official dataset releases from major cloud providers (Microsoft Azure, Alibaba Cloud) and research institutions, and dataset references in surveyed papers. The main text (Table 2) focuses on 11 GPU-relevant traces directly applicable to deep learning prediction, while this appendix (Table 3) catalogs all 22 traces including CPU-only workloads for completeness.

B Evaluation Metrics

The following metrics are commonly used for evaluating duration prediction accuracy:

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** $MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|$. Robust to outliers and preferred for heavy-tailed duration distributions common in cluster workloads.
- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):** $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$. Penalizes larger errors more heavily; assumes approximately Gaussian error distribution.
- **Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):** $MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|\hat{y}_i - y_i|}{|y_i|}$. Scale-independent, enabling comparison across different duration ranges. Undefined for zero values and asymmetric.
- **Percentage Error (PE):** $PE = \frac{|\hat{y} - y|}{y} \times 100\%$. Most common in systems papers; typically reported as median with percentiles.

C Complete Cluster Trace Catalog

This section provides detailed descriptions of each GPU cluster trace summarized in Table 2, followed by a comprehensive catalog (Table 3) including CPU-only traces.

Philly (Jeon et al., 2019) contains 117K jobs collected over Aug–Dec 2017 from Microsoft’s internal cluster, with GPU/CPU/memory utilization at per-minute sampling. It lacks model architecture and batch size information and predates transformer adoption.

Helios (Hu et al., 2021) is the largest publicly available trace with 3.4M jobs (1.6M GPU jobs) across four SenseTime clusters from Apr–Sep 2020. It includes job metadata, status, and timestamps, with an average GPU job duration of 6,652 seconds.

Alibaba GPU series spans 2020–2026 with four releases: GPU-v2020 (Weng et al., 2022) (6,500+ GPUs with 61% training/39% inference), GPU-v2023 (Weng et al., 2023) (6,200+ GPUs studying resource fragmentation), GPU-v2025 (Yang et al., 2025) (20,000+ DLRM inference instances), and GenAI-v2026 (Yanying Lin, 2025; Yanying Lin and Ye, 2026) (diffusion and LLM model serving). These traces capture the evolution of production deep learning workloads over six years.

Azure LLM series provides inference traces spanning 2023–2025: LLM (2023) (Patel et al., 2025), LLM (2024) (Stojkovic et al., 2025), and LMM (2025) (Qiu et al., 2026). These traces uniquely provide input/output token counts, enabling research on sequence-length-dependent prediction for autoregressive models.

Acme (Hu et al., 2024) is the first large-scale LLM training trace with 881K jobs (470K GPU) from Shanghai AI Lab, Mar–Aug 2023. The accompanying paper analyzes InternLM development data including model architecture, batch size, and framework information, though these are not structured fields in the released trace.

Mars (Wang et al., 2025b) provides a unique trace with source code and runtime logs for 500 LLM jobs (7B–100B parameters), enabling semantic-aware prediction research. It is the only trace with job source code, though it is not publicly available.

Organization	Dataset	Scale	Period	CPU	GPU	Time-stamps	Resource Req.	Utilization	Source Code	Public
Microsoft	Philly (Jeon et al., 2019)	117K jobs	Aug–Dec 2017	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
SenseTime	Helios (Hu et al., 2021)	3.4M jobs	Apr–Sep 2020	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Alibaba	v2017 (Alibaba, 2017)	~1,300 machines	2017 (12h)	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	v2018 (Alibaba, 2018)	~4,000 machines	2018 (8d)	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Micro-svc-v2021 (Luo et al., 2021)	20K+ services	2021 (12h)	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Micro-arch-v2022 (Wang et al., 2023)	Large-scale	2022	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	GPU-v2020 (Weng et al., 2022)	6,500+ GPUs	2020	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	GPU-v2023 (Weng et al., 2023)	6,200+ GPUs	2023	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	GPU-v2025 (Yang et al., 2025)	20K+ instances	2025		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
GenAI-v2026 (Yanying Lin, 2025) (Yanying Lin and Ye, 2026)	Large-scale	2026		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
Azure	VM V1 (Cortez et al., 2017)	~2M VMs	2017	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	VM V2 (Cortez et al., 2017)	~2.6M VMs	2019	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Packing (Hadary et al., 2020)	VM requests	2020	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Noise (Freischutz et al., 2025)	483-day bench.	2024	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Functions '19 (Shahrad et al., 2020)	2-week trace	2019	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Functions '21 (Zhang et al., 2021)	2-week trace	2021	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
	Blob (Romero et al., 2021)	Blob access	2020			✓	✓	✓		✓
	LLM '23 (Patel et al., 2025)	1-day trace	2023		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	LLM '24 (Stojkovic et al., 2025)	1-week trace	2024		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	LMM '25 (Qiu et al., 2026)	1-week trace	2025		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Shanghai AI Lab	Acme (Hu et al., 2024)	881K jobs	Mar–Aug 2023	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
SchedMate	Mars (Wang et al., 2025b)	500 jobs	—		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Table 3: Complete catalog of cluster traces for runtime prediction research, including both GPU and CPU-only workloads. The **Public** column indicates whether the trace is publicly available. **Resource Req.** = resource requests (e.g., GPU count, CPU cores). CPU-only traces (Alibaba v2017–Micro-arch-v2022, Azure VM/Functions/Blob) may be useful for general scheduling research but are less directly applicable to deep learning runtime prediction.